

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF VALACYCLOVIR HYDROCHLORIDE SUSTAINED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS

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Article Received: September 2022 Accepted: September 2022 Published: October 2022

Abstract:

The present work is aimed at preparing and evaluating sustained release (SR) matrix tablets of valacyclovir hydrochloride (VH) using different polymers ethylcellulose (EC), hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMCK100, HPMCE4PREMIUM), polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPK 90), xanthum gum (XG) and Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose (NaCMC). In addition, the effect of different diluents (Micro Crystalline Cellulose MCC, Lactose, Di Calcium Phosphate DCP) on drug release was evaluated considering the method of preparation. A total of 18 different formulations were formulated (F1- F18). The blend of all formulations was evaluated for various precompression parameters like angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, Hausner's ratio and were found to be satisfactory. The tablets were evaluated for various parameters like weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, wetting time, water absorption ratio, disintegration time, content uniformity and in vitro drug release. The data was subjected to kinetic analysis and the mechanism of the release was established. The results demonstrated that combination of both hydrophobic and hydrophilic polymers could be successfully employed for formulating sustained release matrix tablets of valacyclovir hydrochloride. The formulation containing drug, polymer (EC) and DCP as a diluent extended the drug release for 22 to 24 hours ($R^2=0.9989$) which was established by subjecting the invitro release data to peppas korsmeyer kinetic analysis. The drug release rate was good with the tablets containing hydrophobic ethylcellulose (EC) polymers compared to with that of hydrophilic polymers (HPMC K 100M and E 4 premium). Erosion was established to be the predominant mechanism of release.

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Please cite this article in B.Nagaraju et al, Formulation Development And Evaluation Of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride Sustained Release Matrix Tablets., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2022; 09(10).

INTRODUCTION:

Most conventional oral drug products, such as tablets and capsules, are formulated to release the active drug immediately after oral administration, to obtain rapid and complete systemic drug absorption. Such immediate-release products result in relatively rapid drug absorption and onset of accompanying pharmacodynamic effects. However, after absorption of the drug from the dosage form is complete, plasma drug concentrations decline according to the drug's pharmacokinetic profile. Eventually, plasma drug concentrations fall below the minimum effective plasma concentration (MEC), resulting in loss of therapeutic activity. Before this point is reached, another dose is usually given if a sustained therapeutic effect is desired. An alternative to administering another dose is to use a dosage form that will provide sustained drug release, and therefore maintain plasma drug concentrations, beyond what is typically seen using immediate-release dosage forms. In recent years, various modified-release drug products have been developed to control the release rate of the drug and/or the time for drug release.

The term modified-release drug product is used to describe products that alter the timing and/or the rate of release of the drug substance. A modified-release dosage form is defined "as one for which the drug-release characteristics of time course and/or location are chosen to accomplish therapeutic or convenience objectives not offered by conventional dosage forms such as solutions, ointments, or promptly dissolving dosage forms as presently recognized".

Several types of modified-release drug products are recognized (**Leon Shargel et al., 2004**).

Extended-release drug products:

A dosage form that allows at least a twofold reduction in dosage frequency as compared to that drug presented as an immediate-release (conventional) dosage form. Examples of extended-release dosage forms include controlled-release, sustained-release, and long-acting drug products.

Delayed-release drug products:

A dosage form that releases a discrete portion or portions of drug at a time or at times other than promptly after administration, although one portion may be released promptly after administration. Enteric-coated dosage forms are the most common delayed-release products.

Targeted-release drug products:

A dosage form that releases drug at or near the intended physiologic site of action. Targeted-release dosage forms may have either immediate- or extended-release characteristics.

The term controlled-release drug product was previously used to describe various types of oral extended-release-rate dosage forms, including sustained-release, sustained-action, prolonged-action, long-action, slow-release, and programmed drug delivery.

1.1. Conventional Drug Delivery System:

Pharmaceutical products designed for oral delivery are mainly conventional drug delivery systems, which are designed for immediate release of drug for rapid/immediate absorption (**Robinson, 1987**).

As can be seen in the graph (Figure 1), administration of the conventional dosage form by extra vascular route does not maintain the drug level in blood for an extended period of time. The short duration of action is due to the inability of conventional dosage form to control temporal delivery.

Figure 1: A hypothetical plasma concentration-time profile from conventional multiple dosing and single doses of sustained and controlled delivery formulations. (MSC = maximum safe concentration, MEC = minimum effective concentration).

The conventional dosage forms like solution; suspension, capsule, tablets and suppository etc. have some limitations such as

- 1) Drugs with short half-life require frequent administration, which increases chances of missing the dose of drug leading to poor patient compliance.
- 2) A typical peak-valley plasma concentration-time profile is obtained which makes attainment of steady state condition difficult. The unavoidable fluctuations in the drug concentration may lead to under medication or overmedication as the steady state concentration values fall or rise beyond the therapeutic range.
- 3) The fluctuating drug levels may lead to precipitation of adverse effects especially of a drug with small therapeutic index, whenever overdosing occurs.

In order to overcome the drawbacks of conventional drug delivery systems, several technical advancements have led to the development of controlled drug delivery system that could revolutionize method of medication and provide a number of therapeutic benefits (Chien, 1992).

1.2. Controlled Release Drug Delivery Systems (CRDDS):

More precisely, controlled delivery can be defined as

- 1) Sustained drug action at a predetermined rate by maintaining a relatively constant, effective drug level in the body with concomitant minimization of undesirable side effects.
- 2) Localized drug action by spatial placement of a controlled release system adjacent to or in the diseased tissue.
- 3) Targeted drug action by using carriers or chemical derivatives to deliver drug to a particular target cell type.
- 4) Provide a physiologically / therapeutically based drug release system. In other words, the amount and the rate of drug release are determined by the physiological/ therapeutic needs of the body.

A controlled drug delivery system is usually designed to deliver the drug at particular rate. Safe and effective blood levels are maintained for a period as long as the system continues to deliver the drug. This predetermined rate of drug release is based on the desired therapeutic concentration and the drug's pharmacokinetics.

1.2.1 Advantages of Controlled Drug Delivery System:

1. Overcome patient compliance problems.
2. Employ less total drug
 - a) Minimize or eliminate local side effects
 - b) Minimize or eliminate systemic side effects

- c) Obtain less potentiation or reduction in drug activity with chronic use.
- d) Minimize drug accumulation with chronic dosing.
3. Improve efficiency in treatment
 - a) Cures or controls condition more promptly.
 - b) Improves control of condition i.e., reduced fluctuation in drug level.
 - c) Improves bioavailability of some drugs.
 - d) Make use of special effects, e.g. Sustained-release aspirin for morning relief of arthritis by dosing before bed time.
4. Economy i.e. reduction in health care costs. The average cost of treatment over an extended time period may be less, with lesser frequency of dosing, enhanced therapeutic benefits and reduced side effects. The time required for health care personnel to dispense and administer the drug and monitor patient is also reduced.

1.2.2. Disadvantages:

- 1) Decreased systemic availability in comparison to immediate release conventional dosage forms, which may be due to incomplete release, increased first-pass metabolism, increased instability, insufficient residence time for complete release, site specific absorption, pH dependent stability etc.
- 2) Poor in vitro – in vivo correlation.
- 3) Retrieval of drug is difficult in case of toxicity, poisoning or hypersensitivity reactions.
- 4) Reduced potential for dose adjustment of drugs normally administered in varying strengths (**Hoffman, 1998**).

1.3. Oral Controlled Drug Delivery Systems:

Oral controlled release drug delivery is a system that provides continuous oral delivery of drugs at predictable and reproducible kinetics for a predetermined period throughout the course of GI transit and also the system that target the delivery of a drug to a specific region within the GI tract for either a local or systemic action (**Vora et al., 1996**).

1.4. Classification of Oral Controlled Release Systems:

A) Diffusion Controlled Systems:

I. Reservoir Devices:

A core of drug (the reservoir) surrounded by a polymeric membrane characterizes them. The nature of the membrane determines the rate of drug release.

The characteristics of reservoir diffusion systems are

1. Zero order drug release is possible.
2. The drug release rate is dependent on the type of polymer.
3. High molecular weight compounds are difficult to deliver through the device. Coating and microencapsulation technique can be used to prepare sub devices.

II. Matrix Devices:

It consists of drug dispersed homogeneously in a matrix. The characteristics of the matrix diffusion system is

1. Zero order release cannot be obtained.
2. Easy to produce than reservoir devices.
3. High molecule weight compounds are delivered through the devices.

B) Dissolution controlled systems:

I. Matrix Dissolution Controlled System:

Aqueous dispersions, congealing, spherical agglomeration etc. can be used.

II. Encapsulation Dissolution Control:

Particles, seeds or granules can be coated by technique such as microencapsulation.

C) Diffusion and Dissolution Controlled System:

In a bioerodible matrix, the drug is homogeneously dispersed in a matrix and it is released either by swelling controlled mechanism or by hydrolysis or by enzymatic attack.

1.5. Types of Extended-Release Products:

General approaches to manufacturing an extended-release drug product include the use of a matrix structure in which the drug is suspended or dissolved, the use of a rate-controlling membrane through which the drug diffuses, or a combination of both. Among the many types of commercial preparations available, none works by a single drug-release mechanism. Most extended-release products release drug by a combination of processes involving dissolution, permeation, and diffusion. The single most important factor is water permeation, without which none of the product release mechanisms would operate. Controlling the rate of water influx into the product generally dictates the rate at which the drug dissolves. Once the drug is dissolved, the rate of drug diffusion may be further controlled to a desirable rate. Table 1 shows some common extended-release product examples and the mechanisms for controlling drug release, and lists the compositions for some drugs (**Leon Shargel, 2004**).

Table 1. Examples of Oral Extended-Release Products

Type	Trade Name	Rationale
Erosion tablet	Constant-T	Theophylline
	Tenuate Dospan	Diethylpropion HCl dispersed in hydrophilic matrix
	Tedral SA	Combination product with a slow-erosion component (theophylline, ephedrine HCl) and an initial-release component theophylline, ephedrine HCl, phenobarbital)
Waxy matrix tablet	Kaon Cl	Slow release of potassium chloride to reduce GI irritation
Coated pellets in capsule	Ornade spansule	Combination phenylpropanolamine HCl and chlorpheniramine with initial- and extended-release component
Pellets in tablet	Theo-Dur	Theophylline
Leaching	Ferro-Gradumet (Abbott)	Ferrous sulfate in a porous plastic matrix that is excreted in the stool; slow release of iron decreases GI irritation
	Desoxyn gradumet tablet (Abbott)	Methamphetamine methylacrylate methylmethacrylate copolymer, povidone, magnesium stearate; the plastic matrix is porous
Coated ion exchange	Tussionex	Cation ion-exchange resin complex of hydrocodone and phenyltoloxamine
Flotation-diffusion	Valrelease	Diazepam
Osmotic delivery	Acutrim	Phenylpropanolamine HCl (Oros delivery system)
	Procardia-XL	GITS—gastrointestinal therapeutic system with NaCl-driven (osmotic pressure) delivery system for nifedipine
Microencapsulation	Bayer timed-release	Aspirin
	Nitrospan	Microencapsulated nitroglycerin
	Micro-K Extencaps	Potassium chloride microencapsulated particles

1.6. Factors Influencing the Design and Performance of Sustained Release Products:

The type of delivery system and route of administration of the drug presented in sustained drug delivery system may depend upon two properties (**Bramhankar and Jaiswal, 1995**). They are

- I. Physicochemical Properties of drugs
- II. Biological Factors.

1.6.1. Physicochemical Properties of Drugs:

1. Dose size:

For orally administered systems, there is an upper limit to the bulk size of the dose to be administered. In general a single dose of 0.5 to 1gm is considered maximum (**Nicholas et al., 1987**).

2. Ionization, P^{Ka} & Aqueous Solubility:

The pH Partition hypothesis simply states that the unchanged form of a drug species will be preferentially absorbed through many body tissues. Therefore it is important to note the relationship between the P^{Ka} of the compound and its absorptive environment. For many compounds, the site of maximum absorption will also be the area in which the drug is least soluble.

For conventional dosage forms the drug can generally

fully dissolve in the stomach and then be absorbed in the alkaline pH of the intestine. For sustained release formulations much of the drug will arrive in the small intestine in solid form. This means that the solubility of the drug is likely to change several orders of magnitude during its release.

Compounds with very low solubility are inherently controlled, since their release over the time course of a dosage form in the GIT will be limited by dissolution of the drug. The lower limit for the solubility of a drug to be formulated in a sustained release system has been reported to be 0.1mg/mL (**Fincher et al., 1968**). Thus for slightly soluble drugs, diffusional systems will be poor choice, since the concentration in solution will be low.

For example Tetracycline has maximum solubility in the stomach and least solubility in the intestine where it is maximally absorbed. Other examples of drugs whose incorporation into sustained release systems are limited because of their poor aqueous solubility and slow dissolution rate are digoxin, warfarrin, griseofulvin and salicylamide. Very soluble drugs are also good candidates for the sustained release dosage forms.

3. Partition coefficient:

The compounds with a relatively high partition

coefficient are predominantly lipid soluble and easily penetrate membranes resulting high bioavailability. Compounds with very low partition coefficient will have difficulty in penetrating membranes resulting poor bioavailability. Furthermore partitioning effects apply equally to diffusion through polymer membranes.

4. Drug Stability:

The drugs, which are unstable in stomach, can be placed in a slowly soluble form and their release delayed until they reach the small intestine. However, such a strategy would be detrimental for drugs that either are unstable in the small intestine (or) undergo extensive gut wall metabolism, as pointed out in the decrease bioavailability of some anticholinergic drugs from controlled /sustained release formulation. In general, the drugs, which are unstable in GIT environment poor candidates for oral sustained release forms.

4. Protein Binding:

It is well known that many drugs bind to plasma proteins with a concomitant influence on the duration of drug action. Since blood proteins are mostly recirculated and not eliminated. Drug protein binding can serve as depot for drug producing a prolonged release profile, especially if a high degree of drug binding occurs.

1.6.2. Biological Factors:

1. Biological Half-Life:

Therapeutic compounds with half-life less than 8 hrs are excellent candidates for sustained release preparations. Drugs with very short half-life (less than 2 hrs) will require excessively large amounts of drug in each dosage unit to maintain controlled effects. Thus forcing the dosage form itself to become too large to be administered. Compounds with relatively long half-lives, generally greater than 8 hrs are not used in the sustained release dosage forms, since their effect is already sustained and also GI transit time is 8-12 hrs (**Jantzen et al., 1996**). So the drugs, which have long -half life and short half-life, are poor candidates for sustained release dosage forms.

Some examples of drug with half-lives of less than 2 hours are ampicillin, cephalixin, cloxacillin, furosemide, levodopa, penicillin G and

propylthiouracil. Examples of those with half-lives of greater than 8 hours are dicumarol, diazepam, digitoxin, digoxin, guanethidine, phenytoin and warfarin.

2. Absorption:

The characteristics of absorption of a drug can greatly affect its suitability as a sustained release product. Drugs which are absorbed by specialized transport process (carrier mediated) and drug absorption at special sites of the gastrointestinal tract (Absorption Window) are poor candidates for sustained release products.

3. Metabolism:

The metabolic conversion of a drug to another chemical form usually can be considered in the design of a sustained-release system for that drug. As long as the location, rate and extent of metabolism are known and the rate constant(s) for the process(es) are not too large, successful sustained-release products can be developed.

There are two factors associated with the metabolism of some drugs; however that present problems of their use in sustained-release systems. One is the ability of the drug to induce or inhibit enzyme synthesis; this may result in a fluctuating drug blood level with chronic dosing. The other is a fluctuating drug blood level due to intestinal (or other tissue) metabolism or through a hepatic first-pass effect.

Examples of drugs that are subject to intestinal metabolism upon oral dosing are hydralazine, salicylamide, nitroglycerine, isoproterenol, chlorpromazine and levodopa. Examples of drugs that undergo extensive first-pass hepatic metabolism are propoxyphene, nortriptyline, phenacetine, propranolol and lidocaine.

Drugs that are significantly metabolized especially in the region of the small intestine can show decreased bioavailability from slower releasing dosage forms. This is due to saturation of intestinal wall enzyme systems. The drugs should not have intestinal first pass effect and should not induce (or) inhibit metabolism are good candidates for sustained release dosage forms. Various technologies used for controlled release drug delivery systems were given in Table 2 (**Chien et al., 1990**).

Table 2. Technologies used for CRDDS :

SL.NO.	DESIGN OR TYPE OF THE SYSTEM	RELEASE MECHANISM
1	Dissolution Controlled CR systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encapsulation (including Micro encapsulation) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Barrier coating - Embedment into a matrix of fatty materials) - Repeat action coatings - Coated plastic materials or hydrophilic materials • Matrix Dissolution Control 	The dissolution of drug from system
2	Diffusion Controlled CR systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reservoir Devices (Fatty polymer coated systems) • Matrix Devices (Fatty polymer dispersed systems) 	The diffusion of the drug solution through a water - insoluble, permeable polymeric film
3	Dissolution and Diffusion Controlled CR systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nondisintegrating polymeric matrix • Hydrophilic matrices 	Diffusion of a drug solution through a porous matrix
4	Ion- Exchange Resin CR Systems:	Ion- Exchange between the resin - drug complex and ions in the GI tract
5	pH - Independent formulations:	Influenced by change in pH and ionic permeability of the membrane coating
6	Osmotically Controlled CR systems:	They contain the buffering agents in a system which maintains constant pH throughout the GIT, so the drug release from the device is not affected by variable pH of GIT. Water entering by Osmosis dissolves the drug, and the drug solution is forced out through a laser drilled orifice
7	Altered - Density systems:	Diffusion from high - density pellets or from floating

1.7. Monolithic Matrix System:

In pharmaceutical CRDDS, matrix based systems are the most commonly used type of release controlling methodology owing to their simple manufacturing process. The preparation of a tablet with the matrix involves the direct compression of the blends of drug, release retardant and other additives, in which the drug is uniformly distribute throughout the matrix core of the release retardant. Alternatively, drug-release retardant blends may be granulated to make the mix suitable for the preparation of tablets by wet granulation or beads (Colombo *et al.*, 1995).

To characterize and define the matrix systems the following properties of the matrix are considered.

1. Chemical nature of the support.
2. The physical state of the drug.
3. The matrix and alteration in volume as the function of the time.

4. The routes of administration.

5. The release kinetics model (in accordance with Higuchi's equation, these system considered to release the drug as a function of square root of time).

The classification of the matrix-based systems is based on the following criteria.

- Matrix structure
- Release kinetics
- Controlled release properties (diffusion, erosion and swelling).
- Chemical nature and the properties of the applied release retardant(s).

Based on the chemical nature of the release retardant(s), the matrix systems are classified as given in Table 3.

Table 3. Classification of Matrix Systems:

Type of the Matrix System	Mechanism
Hydrophilic	- Unlimited swelling delivery by diffusion - Limited swelling-controlled delivery Eg: Hydroxyethylcellulose, Hydroxypropylmethyl cellulose
Inert	- Inert in nature - Controlled delivery by diffusion Eg: Ethylcellulose
Lipidic	- Delivery by diffusion & erosion Eg: Carnauba wax.
Biodegradable	- Non lipidic nature - Controlled delivery by surface erosion
Resin Matrices	- Drug release from drug-resin complex Eg: Ion exchange resins

1.8. Mechanism of Drug Release from Matrix Tablets:

As shown in Figure 2, in erodible matrices, polymer erosion from the surface of the matrix determines the drug release; whilst in hydrophilic matrices, formation of the gel layer and its dynamics as a function of time determines the drug release. Gel layer thickness, which determines the diffusion path length of the drug, corresponds to the distance between the diffusion and erosion fronts. As the swelling process proceeds, the gel layer gradually becomes thicker, resulting in progressively slower drug-release rates; however, due to continuous hydration, polymer disentanglement occurs from the surface of the matrix, resulting in a gradually decreasing depletion zone and an increased dissolution rate.

Figure2. Schematic drug release from matrix diffusion controlled-release drug delivery systems with the drug homogeneously dispersed in: (a) an erodible polymer matrix; and (b) a hydrophilic, swellable polymer matrix.

1.9. Drug Release Kinetics -Model Fitting of the Dissolution Data:

Whenever a new solid dosage form is developed or produced, it is necessary to ensure that drug dissolution occurs in an appropriate manner. The pharmaceutical industry and the registration authorities do focus, nowadays, on drug dissolution studies. Drug dissolution from solid dosage forms has been described by kinetic models in which the dissolved amount of drug (Q) is a function of the test time, t or $Q=f(t)$. Some analytical definitions of the $Q(t)$ function are commonly used, such as zero order, first order, Hixson–Crowell, Higuchi, Korsmeyer–Peppas models. (Mulye and Turco, 1995; Colombo et al., 1999; Kim et al., 1997; Manthena et al., 2004; Desai et al., 1996; Higuchi et al., 1963). Different models expressing drug release kinetics were given in Table 4

Zero order kinetics

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0 t$$

Where Q_t is the amount of drug dissolved in time t ,

Q_0 is the initial amount of drug in the solution (most times, $Q_0=0$) and

K_0 is the zero order release constant.

$$f_t = K_0 t$$

where $f_t = 1-(W_t/W_0)$ and f_t represents the fraction of drug dissolved in time t and

K_0 the apparent dissolution rate constant or zero order release constant.

In this way, a graphic of the drug-dissolved fraction versus time will be linear if the previously established conditions were fulfilled.

Use: This relation can be used to describe the drug dissolution of several types of modified release pharmaceutical dosage forms, as in the case of some transdermal systems, as well as matrix tablets with low soluble drugs, coated forms, osmotic systems, etc. The pharmaceutical dosage forms following this profile release the same amount of drug by unit of time and it is the ideal method of drug release in order to achieve a pharmacological prolonged action.

First order kinetics

Kinetic equation for the first order release is as follows:

$$\text{Log } Q_t = \text{log } Q_0 + K_1 t / 2.303$$

where Q_t is the amount of drug released in time t ,

Q_0 is the initial amount of drug in the solution and

K_1 is the first order release constant.

In this way a graphic of the decimal logarithm of the released amount of drug versus time will be linear. The pharmaceutical dosage forms following this dissolution profile, such as those containing water-soluble drugs in porous matrices, release the drug in a way that is proportional to the amount of drug remaining in its interior, in such way, that the amount of drug released by unit of time diminishes.

Higuchi model

$$f_t = K_H t^{1/2}$$

Where K_H is the Higuchi dissolution constant treated sometimes in a different manner by different authors and theories.

Higuchi describes drug release as a diffusion process based in the Fick's law, square root time dependent. This relation can be used to describe the drug dissolution from several types of modified release pharmaceutical dosage forms, as in the case of some transdermal systems and matrix tablets with water-soluble drugs.

Hixson–Crowell model

Hixson and Crowell (1931) recognizing that the particle regular area is proportional to the cubic root of its volume derived an equation that can be described in the following manner

$$W_0^{1/3} - W_t^{1/3} = K_s t$$

Where W_0 is the initial amount of drug in the pharmaceutical dosage form,

W_t is the remaining amount of drug in the pharmaceutical dosage form at time t and

K_s is a constant incorporating the surface–volume relation.

This expression applies to pharmaceutical dosage form such as tablets, where the dissolution occurs in planes that are parallel to the drug surface if the tablet dimensions diminish proportionally, in such a manner that the initial geometrical form keeps constant all the time.

A graphic of the cubic root of the unreleased fraction of drug versus time will be linear if the equilibrium conditions are not reached and if the geometrical shape of the pharmaceutical dosage form diminishes proportionally over time. This model has been used to describe the release profile keeping in mind the diminishing surface of the drug particles during the dissolution

Mechanism of Drug Release based on kinetics:

To find out the drug release mechanism due to swelling (upon hydration) along with gradual erosion of the matrix, first 60% drug release data can be fitted in Korsmeyer–Peppas model which is often used to describe the drug release behavior from polymeric systems when the mechanism is not well-known or when more than one type of release phenomena is involved (Korsmeyer *et al.*, 1983).

$$\text{Log } (M_t / M_\infty) = \text{Log } K_{KP} + n \text{ Log } t$$

Where, M_t is the amount of drug release at time t , M_∞ is the amount of drug release after infinite time, K_{KP} is a release rate constant incorporating structural and geometrical characteristics of the tablet and n is the release exponent indicative of the mechanism of drug release.

Table 4. Drug Release Kinetics:

Kinetic Model	Relation	Systems Following the Model
First order	$\ln Q_t = \ln Q_0 + K_t$ (Release is proportional to amount of drug remaining)	Water-soluble drugs in porous matrix
Zero order	$f_t = K_0 t$ (Independent of drug concentration)	Transdermal systems Osmotic systems
Higuchi	$f_t = K_H t^{1/2}$ (Proportional to square root of time)	Matrix formulations
Hixson-Crowell	$W_0^{1/3} - W_t^{1/3} = K_s t$	Erodible isometric matrices

f_t = fraction of dose release at time 't';

K_H , K_0 , and K_s = release rate constants characteristic to respective models;

Q_0 = the drug amounts remaining to be released at zero hour;

Q_t = the drug amounts remaining to be released at time 't';

W_0 = initial amount of drug present in the matrix;

W_t = amount of drug released at time 't'.

7. METHODOLOGY:**Table:6 LIST OF MATERIALS**

S.No.	Material	Manufactured by
1	Valacyclovir Hydrochloride(BP/USP)	Ven petro chem. and pharma Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
2	HPMC K100 M	Cadila Pharma,Ahmedabad
3	HPMC E ₄ premium	Cadila pharma, Ahmedabad
4	Ethyl Cellulose	Vilin Biomed,New Delhi
5	Povidone K90	Glenmark Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Mumbai
6	Na CMC	Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
7	Xanthum Gum	Glenmark Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Mumbai
8	Micro Crystalline Cellulose (Avicel PH-101)	Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
9	Loactose Monohydrate	Qualikems Fine Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.,New Delhi
10	Dicalcium Phosphate	S.D. Fine Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.,Mumbai.
11	Magnesium Stearate	Finar Chemicals Ltd.,Ahmedabad
12	Sodium Hydroxide Pellets	Qualikems Fine Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.,New Delhi
Reagents		
13	Hydrochloric acid	Qualikems Fine Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.,New Delhi
14	Buffer Solution	Merck Specialities Pvt.Ltd.,Mumbai.

Table:7 LIST OF INSTRUMENTS

S.No	Instrument	Manufacturer
1	Electronoic Weighing Balance	Shimadzu,AUX220,Japan.
2	16 Station Rotary Tableting machine	Cadmach Machinery Co.,Ahmedabad, India.
3	Tap Density Tester (USP)	Electro lab , ETD-1020,India
4	Hardness Tester (Monsanto)	Cadmach Machinery Co.,Ahmedabad, India
5	Digital Vernier Calipers	Mitutoyo Corp,Kawasaki. Japan.
6	Sieves	Rolex Standard Sieves, Hyderabad, India.
7	Dissolution Apparatus (USP)	Electro Lab,TDT-08L,India.
8	UV/Visible Spectrophotometer	Systronics PC Based 2202, Ahmedabad,India.
9	Hot Air Oven	Biotechnics Pvt. Ltd., India.
10	Friability Test Apparatus	Campbell Electronics, Mumbai,India.
11	pH Meter	LI 120,Elico Pvt.Ltd.,India.

Construction of Standard Graph of Valacyclovir hydrochloride:

Accurately weighed amount of 68 mg valacyclovir hydrochloride was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask. 20 mL of 0.1 N hydrochloric acid (HCl) was added to dissolve the drug and volume was made up to 100 mL with the same HCl. The resulted solution had the concentration of 1mg/ml which was labeled as 'stock'. From this stock solution 2ml was taken and diluted to 50 mL with 0.1N HCl which has given the solution having the concentration of 50 mcg/mL.

The absorbances of above solutions were recorded at X_{max} (255 nm) of the drug using double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Standard graph was plotted between the concentration (on X-axis) and absorbance (on Y-axis).

Similarly, standard graph was plotted with 6.8 pH phosphate buffer, 4.5 pH phosphate buffer.

Preparation of 0.1 N HCl:

Accurately measured 85 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to 10000 mL of distilled water,

Preparation of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer:

Accurately measured 50 mL of 0.2 M potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate was transferred to a 200mL volumetric flask and 22.4 mL of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide was added to it. Volume was made up to 200 mL with distilled water, mixed and pH was adjusted to 6.8 with 0.2 M sodium hydroxide or 0.2 M othophosphoric acid.

Preparation of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide solution:

Accurately weighed 8 g of sodium hydroxide pellets were dissolved in 1000 mL of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride Matrix Tablets

All the matrix tablets, each containing 500 mg of valacyclovir hydrochloride, were prepared by direct compression method to study the effect of method of manufacture on the drug release.

Direct compression:

Accurately weighed amounts of drug, polymer, and diluent were mixed geometrically in a mortar. This mixture was passed through No.40 sieve and thoroughly mixed in a polythene bag for 15 minutes. The magnesium stearate is then passed through No.60 sieve and mixed with powder blend and mixed thoroughly in the polythene bag for 2 minutes and compressed into tablets on a 16-station rotary tableting machine using 16x14mm caplet shaped punches

The drug polymer ratio was developed to adjust drug release as per theoretical release profile and to keep total weight of tablet constant for all the fabricated batches under experimental conditions of preparations. The total weight of the matrix tablets was 700mg. The various polymers used were HPMC K100, HPMC E4Premium, Povidone K90, Xanthum gum, Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose and Ethyl cellulose. Diluents like MCC (water-insoluble), lactose (water soluble) and DCP (erosion) were used for the preparation of matrix tablets.

Table: 8 List of Different Formulations

Formulae	Polymer (s)	Diluent	Method
F1 toF3	Ethyl cellulose	MCC, Lactose, DCP	Direct compression
F4 toF6	HPMC K100	MCC, Lactose, DCP	Direct compression
F7 to F9	HPMC E4 Premium	MCC, Lactose, DCP	Direct compression
F10toF12	Povidone K90	MCC, Lactose, DCP	Direct compression
F13toF15	Xanthum Gum	MCC, Lactose, DCP	Direct compression
F16toF18	NaCMC	MCC, Lactose, DCP	Direct compression

Formulations

In the formulations prepared, the release retardants included were ethyl cellulose (EC), hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC K100, HPMC E4 PREMIUM), polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPK 90), xanthum gum (XG), and Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose (NaCMC). Micro crystal line cellulose (MCC), Lactose, and Di calcium phosphorate (DCP) were used as diluents, Magnesium stearate (MS) 1.4% was used as was lubricants. 11.14% w/v solution of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP-K90) was used as polymer used as binder. Compositions of different formulations are given in table.3

Table:9 Composition of Matrix Tablets Containing HPMC K 100 in lactose, MCC102, DCP

F CODE	VH (mg)	Ethyl cellulose (mg)	HPMC K100 M (mg)	HPMC E4 premium (mg)	PVP k90 (mg)	NaCMC (mg)	MG STERATE (mg)	XANTHUM GUM (mg)	LACTOSE (mg)	MCC 102 (mg)	DCP (mg)
FI	500	80					10		110		
FII	500	80					10			110	
FIII	500	80					10				110
FIV	500		80				10		110		
FV	500		80				10			110	
FVI	500		80				10				110
FVII	500			80			10		110		
FIII	500			80			10			110	
FIX	500			80			10				110
FX	500				78		10		112		
FXI	500				78		10			112	
FXII	500				78		10				112
FXIII	500					42	10		110		
FXIV	500					42	10			110	
FXV	500					42	10				110
FXVI	500						10	35	110		
FXVII	500						10	35		110	
FXVIII	500					10	35				110

Evaluation of Precompression Blend

a) Angle of Repose

The angle of repose of granules was determined by the funnel-method. The accurately weighed granules were taken in a funnel. The height of the funnel was adjusted in such a manner that the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the heap of the granules. The granules were allowed to flow through the funnel freely onto the surface. The diameter of the powder cone measured and angle of repose was calculated using the following equation (Raghuram et al., 2003).

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

where h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone, θ is the angle of repose.

Angle of repose values less than 25, 25-30, 30-40, and more than 40 indicates excellent, good, passable, and poor flow properties respectively.

b) Determination of Bulk Density and Tapped Density

An accurately weighed quantity of the granules/powder (W) was carefully poured into the graduated cylinder and volume (V_0) was measured. Then the graduated cylinder was closed with lid and set into the tap density tester (USP). The density apparatus was set for 100 tabs and after that the volume (V_f) was measured and continued operation till the two consecutive readings were equal (Lachman et al., 1987).

The bulk density and the tapped density were calculated using the following formulae.

$$\text{Bulk density} = W/V_0$$

$$\text{Tapped density} = W/V_f$$

Where, W= Weight of the powder

V_0 = Initial volume

V_f = final volume

c) Compressibility Index (Carr's Index)

Carr's index (CI) is an important measure that can be obtained from the bulk and tapped densities. In theory, the less compressible a material the more flowable it is (Lachman et al., 1987).

$$CI = (TD-BD) \times 100/TD$$

where, TD is the tapped density and BD is the bulk density

Table:10 Carr's Index Values

S.No.	Carr's Index	Properties
1	5-12	Free flowing
2	13-16	Good
3	18-21	Fair
4	23-35	Poor
5	33-38	Very poor
6	>40	Extremely poor

d) Hausner's Ratio

It is the ratio of tapped density and bulk density. Hausner found that this ratio was related to interparticle friction and, as such, could be used to predict powder flow properties (Lachman et al, 1987). Generally a value less than 1.25 indicates good flow properties, which is equivalent to 20% of Carr's index.

Evaluation of Matrix Tablets

i) Thickness

Twenty tablets from the representative sample were randomly taken and individual tablet thickness was measured by using digital vernier caliper. Average thickness and standard deviation values were calculated

ii) Hardness

Tablet hardness was measured by using Monsanto hardness tester. From each batch six tablets were measured for the hardness and average of six values was noted along with standard deviations.

iii) Friability Test

From each batch, ten tablets were accurately weighed and placed in the friability test apparatus (Roche friabilator). Apparatus was operated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes and tablets were observed while rotating. The tablets were then taken after 100 rotations, dedusted and reweighed. The friability was calculated as the percentage weight loss.

Note: No tablet should stick to the walls of the apparatus. If so, brush the walls with talcum powder. There should be no capping also.

% friability was calculated as follows

$$\% \text{ Friability} = (W_1 - W_2) \times 100/W_1$$

where W_1 = Initial weight of the 20 tablets.

W_2 = Final weight of the 20 tablets after testing.

Friability values below 0.8% are generally acceptable,

iv) Weight Variation Test

To study weight variation individual weights (W_j) of 20 tablets from each formulation were noted using electronic balance. Their average weight (W_A) was calculated. Percent weight variation was calculated as follows. Average weights of the tablets along with standard deviation values were calculated.

$$\% \text{ weight variation} = (W_A - W_j) \times 100 / W_A$$

As the total tablet weight was 120 mg, according to IP 1996, out of twenty tablets $\pm 7.5\%$ variation can be allowed for not more than two tablets.

According to USP 2004, $\pm 10\%$ weight variation can be allowed for not more than two tablets out of twenty tablets.

v) Drug Content (Assay)

The drug content of the matrix tablets was determined according to in-house standards and it meets the requirements if the amount of the active ingredient in each of the 10 tested tablets lies within the range of 90% to 110% of the standard amount.

Ten tablets were weighed and taken into a mortar and crushed into fine powder. An accurately weighed portion of the powder equivalent to about 100 mg of TM was transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask containing 70 mL of 0.1 N HCl. It was shaken by mechanical means for 1h. Then it was filtered through a Whatman filter paper (No. 1) and diluted to 100 mL with 0.1N HCl. From this resulted solution 1 mL was taken, diluted to 50 mL with 0.1N HCl and absorbance was measured against blank at 295 nm.

vi) In -Vitro Drug Release Characteristics:

Drug release was assessed by dissolution test under the following conditions: $n = 3$, USP type II dissolution apparatus (paddle method) at 100 rpm in 500 mL of 0.1N HCl for first 2 hours and the phosphate buffer pH 6.8 from 3 to 12 hours, maintained at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. An aliquot (5mL) was withdrawn at specific time intervals and replaced with the same volume of prewarmed ($37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$) fresh dissolution medium. The samples withdrawn were filtered through Whatman filter paper (No. 1) and drug content in each sample was analyzed by UV-visible spectrophotometer at 295 nm.

vii) Kinetic Analysis of Dissolution Data:

To analyze the *in vitro* release data various kinetic models were used to describe the release kinetics. The zero order rate Eq. (1) describes the systems where the drug release rate is independent of its concentration (**Hadjiioannou *et al.*, 1993**). The first order Eq. (2) describes the release from system where release rate is concentration dependent (**Bourne,**

2002). **Higuchi (1963)** described the release of drugs from insoluble matrix as a square root of time dependent process based on Fickian diffusion Eq. (3). The Hixson-Crowell cube root law Eq. (4) describes the release from systems where there is a change in surface area and diameter of particles or tablets (**Hixson and Crowell, 1931**).

$$C = K_0 \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where, K_0 is zero-order rate constant expressed in units of concentration/time and t is the time.

$$\text{Log}C - \text{Log}C_0 - K_1 t / 2.303 \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

where, C_0 is the initial concentration of drug and K_1 is first order constant.

$$Q_n = K_{Ht}^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

where, K_H is the constant reflecting the design variables of the system.

$$Q_0^{1/3} - Q_t^{1/3} - K_{Hct} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

where, Q_t is the amount of drug remained in time t , Q_0 is the initial amount of the drug in tablet and K_{HC} is the rate constant for Hixson-Crowell rate equation.

The following plots were made using the in-vitro drug release data

Cumulative % drug release vs. time (Zero order kinetic model); Log cumulative of % drug remaining vs. time (First order kinetic model);

Cumulative % drug release vs. square root of time (Higuchi model);

And cube root of initial concentration minus the cube root of percentage of drug remaining in the matrix vs. time (Hixson – Crowell cube root law).

viii) Mechanism of drug release

Korsmeyer *et al* (1983) derived a simple relationship which described drug release from a polymeric system Eq. (5). To find out the mechanism of drug release, first 60% drug release data was fitted in Korsmeyer-Peppas model

$$M_t / M_\infty = Kt^n \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

where M_t / M_∞ is fraction of drug released at time t , K is the release rate constant incorporating structural and geometric characteristics of the tablet, and n is the release exponent. The n value is used to characterize different release mechanisms.

A plot of log cumulative % drug release vs. log time was made. Slope of the line was n . The n value is used

to characterize different release mechanisms as given in Table 6, for the cylindrical shaped matrices. Case-II generally refers to the erosion of the polymeric chain and anomalous transport (Non-Fickian) refers to a combination of both diffusion and erosion controlled-drug release (Peppas, 1985).

Table:11 Diffusion Exponent and Solute Release Mechanism for Cylindrical Shape

Diffusion exponent (n)	Overall solute diffusion mechanism
0.45	Fickian diffusion
0.45 <n< 0.89	Anomalous (non-Fickian)
0.89	Case-II transport
n>0.89	Super case-II transport

xi) FTIR Studies

FTIR studies were performed on drug and the optimized formulation using Shimadzu FTIR (Shimadzu Corp., India). The samples were analyzed between wave numbers 4000 and 400 cm^{-1}

xii) Stability Studies

The optimized matrix tablets were subjected to stability studies at $25^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ 60% \pm 5% RH and $40^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ /75% \pm 5% RH the products were evaluated for their physical characteristics, drug content, and in-vitro drug release profiles over a period of 3 months.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

7.1. Standard Graph of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride

The standard graph of valacyclovir hydrochloride has shown good linearity with R values and in 0.1 N HCl and pH 6.8 buffer respectively, which suggests that it obeys the "Beer-Lambert's law".

Table:12 Standard Graph of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride

Cone. (mcg/mL)	Absorbance	
	0.1NHCl	6.8 P ^H Buffer
0	0	0
2	0.0819	0.09
4	0.1491	0.19
6	0.2295	0.28
8	0.3006	0.36
10	0.3669	0.45
R ²	0.998	0.998

Figure:4 Standard Graph of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride in 0.1N HCl

Figure:5 Standard Graph of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride in 6.8 P^H buffer

Dose Calculations and Theoretical Release Profile

As calculated before, the total dose required for once-daily SR formulation of valacyclovir hydrochloride was found to be 500 mg and its theoretical release profile was given in Table 21.

Table:13 Theoretical Release Profile of valacyclovir hydrochloride from SR tablets

Time (hours)	Cumulative % Release
0	0
1	26.49
2	35.47
4	48.65
6	58.53
8	64.28
10	71.52
12	79.13
16	86.22
20	94.31
24	102.98

Characterization of Granules

The granules for matrix tablets were characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, and drug content. Angle of repose was less than 40 and Carr's index values were less than 21 for the granules of all the batches indicating good to fair flow ability and compressibility. Hausner's ratio was less than 1.25 for all the batches indicating good flow properties. The drug content was more than 90 % for all the granules of different formulations.

Table:14 Physical Properties of Precompression Blend

Formulations	Angle of repose (°)	Bulk Density (g/mL)	Tapped Density (g/mL)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	25.49	0.214	0.251	14.74	1.17
F2	26.24	0.308	0.364	15.38	1.18
F3	29.05	0.276	0.322	14.28	1.16
F4	26.97	0.341	0.388	12.11	1.13
F5	29.25	0.324	0.376	13.82	1.16
F6	32.27	0.320	0.397	19.39	1.24
F7	33.65	0.521	0.629	17.17	1.20
F8	33.21	0.518	0.627	17.38	1.21
F9	26.56	0.422	0.506	16.60	1.19
F10	28.75	0.481	0.572	15.90	1.18
F11	27.33	0.475	0.566	16.07	1.19
F12	25.38	0.524	0.599	12.52	1.14
F13	26.43	0.412	0.483	14.69	1.17
F14	24.77	0.488	0.537	9.12	1.10
F15	26.42	0.439	0.521	15.73	1.18
F16	28.19	0.559	0.649	13.94	1.16
F17	29.58	0.331	0.393	15.77	1.18
F18	28.73	0.362	0.428	15.42	1.18

7.3. Physical Evaluation of matrix tablets

Table:15 Physical evaluation of matrix tablets

F.Code	Hardness (kg/cm^2) t	Thickness (mm) t	Weight	Friability (%)	Drug content *
F1	15.50	4.22±0.17	701.8±1.48	0.36	98.25±1.37
F2	15.50±0.31	4.37±0.25	702.4±0.54	0.39	95.28±0.80
F3	15.58±0.40	4.14±0.80	698.6±0.41	0.43	99.12±2.47
F4	15.66±0.55	4.20±0.20	697.8±1.64	0.12	101.22±0.88
F5	14.25±0.57	4.08±0.66	698.6±1.14	0.54	100.24±1.25
F6	14.08±0.30	4.33±0.25	700.2±0.83	0.58	99.53±1.87
F7	14.25±0.57	3.24±0.71	701.9±0.67	0.64	93.28±1.99
F8	14.41±0.60	3.32±0.89	702.0±0.43	0.37	95.35±1.14
F9	15.00±0.44	4.38±0.73	705.5±0.80	0.77	96.34±2.18
F10	15.00±0.31	4.00±0.68	697.2±0.83	0.42	91.29±0.98
F11	15.08±0.37	3.98±0.88	700.1±0.93	0.48	97.35±0.43
F12	15.41±0.70	4.11±0.36	700.2±0.97	0.15	98.88±0.88
F13	14.33±0.50	3.06±0.46	701.2±0.83	0.27	94.57±1.22
F14	14.58±0.57	3.98±0.38	702.2±0.92	0.29	90.35±2.09
F15	14.75±0.77	3.25±0.37	704.0±0.22	0.53	99.54±2.15
F16	14.11±0.80	4.24±0.52	701.8±1.48	0.64	102.55±2.31
F17	15.08±0.86	4.15±0.56	698.4±1.04	0.71	93.78±0.56
F18	15.16±0.75	4.20±0.44	700.4±1.09	0.42	96.27±1.88

All values represent mean ± Standard Deviation (SD), n=3

All values represent mean ± Standard Deviation (SD), n=6

All values represent mean ± Standard Deviation (SD), n=2

The results of the uniformity of weight, hardness, thickness, friability, and drug content of the tablets are shown in Table 18. All the tablets of different batches complied with the official requirements of uniformity of weight as their weights varied between 118.4 and 122.3 mg. The hardness of the tablets ranged from 5.08 to 6.16 kg/cm^2 and the friability values were less than 0.8% indicating that the matrix tablets were compact and hard. The thickness of the tablets ranged from 2.88 to 3.40 mm. All the formulations satisfied the content of the drugs as they contained 90 to 103% of valacyclovir hydrochloride and good uniformity in drug content was observed. Thus all the physical attributes of the prepared tablets were found to be practically within control.

Table:16 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from Ethyl Cellulose

SNO	TIME	%Cumulative Drug Release		
		FI	FII	FIII
1	0	0	0	0
2	1	20.14	21.35	26.49
3	2	28.25	30.14	35.47
4	4	36.45	39.25	48.65
5	6	45.68	42.58	58.53
6	8	52.36	57.25	64.28
7	10	58.68	65.24	71.52
8	12	64.89	72.31	79.13
9	16	73.45	79.35	86.22
10	20	84.89	86.87	94.31
11	24	93.1	95.22	102.98

Figure:6 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from Ethyl Cellulose

Table:17 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from HPMC K100M

SNO	TIME	%Cumulative Drug Release		
		FIV	FV	FVI
1	0	0	0	0
2	1	25.47	25.12	28.14
3	2	31.22	30.58	32.14
4	4	39.55	48.15	45.26
5	6	46.87	52.14	56.88
6	8	54.11	59.03	61.33
7	10	60.85	65.99	68.98
8	12	68.66	72.31	77.68
9	16	72.58	78.74	85.22
10	20	82.66	86.44	93.14
11	24	93.01	96.22	98.14

Figure:7 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from HPMC K100M

Table:18 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from HPMC E4 PREMIUM

SNO	TIME	%Cumulative Drug Release		
		FVII	FVIII	FIX
1	0	0	0	0
2	1	21.88	24.21	22.01
3	2	28.17	30.11	36.14
4	4	33.74	39.24	42.78
5	6	44.23	44.4	56.21
6	8	51.83	55.77	61.25
7	10	63.92	62.55	70.01
8	12	77.5	76.17	78.25
9	16	82.54	85.71	85.68
10	20	91.45	90.34	90.54
11	24	97.28	96.89	98.21

Figure:8 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from HPMC E4 PREMIUM

Table:19 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from POVIDONE K90

SNO	TIME	%Cumulative Drug Release		
		FX	FXI	FXII
1	0	0	0	0
2	1	19.25	22.34	22.56
3	2	26.35	34.43	33.98
4	4	38.14	43.48	39.01
5	6	45.77	56.25	46.59
6	8	57.25	66.72	54.57
7	10	62.89	75.81	68.89
8	12	70.58	83.54	76.98
9	16	81.88	89.45	82.65
10	20	92.14	94.57	89.44
11	24	99.12	99.98	92.68

Figure:9 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from POVIDONE K90

Table:20 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from NACMC

SNO	TIME	% Cumumative Drug Release		
		FXIU	FXIV	FXV
1	0	0	0	0
2	1	23.45	22.38	20.22
3	2	34.58	34.01	30.5
4	4	40.67	42.44	37.54
5	6	48.56	49.59	49
6	8	58.54	56.25	58.25
7	10	66.34	62.54	64.58
8	12	72.56	76.56	74.54
9	16	83.45	82.69	85.2
10	20	89.56	87.54	89.98
11	24	95.89	98.76	98.58

Figure:10 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from NACMC

Table:21 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from XANTHUM GUM

SNO	TIME	%Cumulative Drug Release		
		FXVI	FXVII	FXVIII
1	0	0	0	0
2	1	20.32	20.34	22.36
3	2	30.12	32.45	33.45
4	4	38.54	40.01	42.54
5	6	45.56	49.86	53.54
6	8	52.02	56.95	59.32
7	10	59.35	68.98	66.21
8	12	66.56	76.91	79.21
9	16	78.58	81.98	86.64
10	20	82.01	89.23	92.34
11	24	92.13	96.45	98

Figure:11 Invitro release of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride from XANTHUM GUM

Table:22 Zero Order Graph of Optimized Formulation(III)

SNO	TIME	%Cumulative Drug Release
		FIII
1	1	26.49
2	2	35.47
3	4	48.65
4	6	58.53
5	8	64.28
6	10	71.52
7	12	79.13
8	16	86.22
9	20	94.31
10	24	102.98

Figure:12 Zero order graph of optimized formulation III

Table:23 FIRST Order Graph of Optimized Formulation (FIII)

SL NO.	TIME	Log % Remaining
		FIII
1	1	1.866346
2	2	1.809762
3	4	1.71054
4	6	1.617734
5	8	1.552911
6	10	1.45454
7	12	1.319522
8	16	1.139249
9	20	0.755112
10	24	#NUM!

Figure:13 First Order Graph of Optimised Formulation III

Table:24 Higuchi Plot of Optimized Formulation (FIII)

SNO	(TIME) ^{1/2}	%Cumulative Drug Release
		FIII
1	1	26.49
2	1.414214	35.47
3	2	48.65
4	2.44949	58.53
5	2.828427	64.28
6	3.162278	71.52
7	3.464102	79.13
8	4	86.22
9	4.472136	94.31
10	4.898979	102.98

Figure:14 Higuchi Plot of Optimised Formulation III

Table:25 Korsmeyer-Peppas Graph of Optimized Formulation (FIII)

SNO	LOG TIME	LOG(M ₀ /M _A)
		FIII
1	0	-0.576918
2	0.30103	-0.4501388
3	0.60206	-0.3129172
4	0.7781513	-0.2326215
5	0.90309	-0.1919241
6	1	-0.1455725
7	1.0791812	-0.1016588
8	1.20412	-0.064392
9	1.30103	-0.0254423
10	1.3802112	0.01275289

Figure:15 Korsmeyer-Peppas Graph of Optimised Formulation III

For understanding the mechanism of drug release and release rate kinetics of the drug from dosage form, the invitro drug diffusion data obtained was fitted to various mathematical models such as zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix, korsmeyer-peppas model. The % drug release with data fitting to various kinetic models for different formulations is presented in figure 12 to figure 15.

Of all the plots of optimized formulation III the R value of model korsmeier-peppas were close to 1. The diffusion exponent (n) value is 0.427 so the drug transport follows Fickian transport. If $n < 0.5$, the polymer relaxation does not affect the molecular transport, hence diffusion is Fickian.

Spectra 1: IR Spectra of Valacyclovir Hydrochloride

Spectra 2: IR Spectra of Optimised Formulation III

9. CONCLUSION AND SUMMARY:

Results of the present study of matrix tablets of valacyclovir hydrochloride demonstrated that combination of both hydrophobic polymers could be successfully employed for formulating sustained-release matrix tablets of valacyclovir hydrochloride.

All the formulations containing drug, polymer and DCP as a diluent extended the drug release for 22 to 24 hours.

The drug release rate was good with the tablets containing hydrophobic EC polymers compared to with that of hydrophilic polymers (HPMC K100M and E 4 premium). Erosion was the dominating release mechanism for the formulations containing povidone.

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